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**Perception of Noise Pollution Effects on Human Health in Rumueme Community,
Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State**

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to determine the perception of noise pollution effects on human health resident in Rumueme community, Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study employed a descriptive research design. The population was 61109 and sample size of 611 derived thereof. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured, validated questionnaire. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the community survey. All respondents in alternate households were selected. The properly filled copies of the questionnaire retrieved were 351 out of 380 issued given cautious physical contact during COVID-19 pandemic. Data obtained was summarized, and then presented in frequency tables and percentage. The majority (41.88%) perception was on the presence of high noise intensity in Rumueme Community. The affirmative mental health effects of noise pollution found included annoyance (49.29%), reduced comprehension and memory (55.84%), and hearing impairment (44.73%). Among its social adverse health effects perceived were undermined community security (44.73%) and increased crime rate (46.72%). The physical untoward health effects noted included violence proneness from quick anger (55.55%), injury from the fight (60.68%), and abnormally high blood pressure (46.15%). The study recommended further enlightenment campaign on the danger of effects of noise pollution to human health, the authority to consider the protection of the populace from noise pollution as an integral part of their policy on environmental protection, enacting legislation to reduce sound pressure levels with existing legislation being enforced as a matter of necessity, and individuals and governments promoting the use of noiseless machinery and automobiles to reduce noise generation.

Keywords: Perception, noise pollution, effects, human health, Rumueme Community.